

INFLUENCE OF AMERICAN TV SHOWS ON UNIVERSITY STUDENTS OF LAHORE: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF 3 DECADES (1990-2020)

Maria Sabir Rana

Abstract

The culture and traditions of a country are very closely related to media content as many studies have shown that the media content not only influences the culture but also shapes it, and vice versa. The influence of popular and dominant media content is visible across the globe. Globalization has threatened the individuality, identity, and culture of different nations. This research aims to explore the influence of American TV shows on the culture, especially on the language, dress, cultural preferences, and social behaviors of university students of Lahore. The sample for this study was taken from four different universities in Lahore. The methods used for this study are in-depth interviews of heavy viewers and a survey. The findings of this study strongly advocate for the proposition that American TV shows have a very strong influence on the social behaviors, cultural preferences, language, and dress of university students of Lahore. It is quite evident that these shows have had a primarily detrimental impact on our culture as a whole. Our youth is now more attuned to American culture and values, thanks to these shows.

Keywords: *Influence, American TV shows, Social behaviors, Cultural preferences, ~~Youth~~*

Introduction

One of the most crucial methods to assimilate into a society and its culture is through mass media. They not only provide knowledge and entertainment but also play a significant role in influencing the masses and cultural propagation. Whether we like it or not, media play a major part in defining our worldviews, ideologies, and beliefs as independent individuals as well as a whole community.

Television has a very deep and very long-lasting effect on human psychology. A lot of social science research presents that the shows people watch on television influence them in various ways. As per Bogart (1956) "with no other form of impersonal communication has the sharing of experience been possible on so universal a scale and to so intense a degree as with television" (p. 2).

The quality of content that audiences consume influences their thinking, political preferences, and dislikes and it even affects the cognitive capabilities of its viewers. Modern researchers have focused on the influence of foreign content on international viewers, leading to the result that heavy viewers of foreign content tend to adopt it. Bringing up the cultural hegemony of American media, Schiller (1969) contends that what sets America apart from past historical realms is its major dependence on mass media rather than the military to bring nations across the world under its influence.

The scope and character of media/cultural imperialism have been the subject of a continuous and intense discourse since the early 1970s. The underlying question of the argument has been if Western media content like television and movies undermines conventional customs and inhibits local cultures of third-world nations.

Well, Heavy viewership of foreign content on television not only makes the viewers normalize foreign traditions and culture, but it also in some sort, influences them to develop the same. This makes them believe that whatever is shown to them is true and it is perfectly alright to follow those traditions, may it be cultural preferences or their fashion trends. A survey conducted by Nazir & Ali (2019) from respondents who had never been to any western country before, revealed that their exposure to western culture through TV shows had caused the viewers to form an alien cultural world in their minds and a significant degree of perceptual disbelief against local culture and inclination towards western culture was measured, which resulted in form of dissatisfaction among viewers of western content.

This can be reckoned by the formation of "The Television without Frontiers directive 1989", which was an attempt by European legislators to limit the volume of US television shows being broadcast in Europe. Through this, the members of the European Union (EU) were required to assure, where feasible and suitable, that transmitters retain European media more. Whereas many EU members disregarded the quota restricting US content to a certain percentage of European television, nations like France and England firmly backed restrictions on US media imports. Given that effort to establish a protective policy regarding culture that demonstrates some degree of caution regarding the possible detrimental impact of US culture on European society.

In the present case, the rapid increase in viewership of American shows is because of the availability of them easily on social sites such as Netflix. These shows not only entertain the audience but also, in a very subtle way, portray their own culture and traditions. The people who binge-watch these shows are mostly teenagers or university students. The viewership has increased gradually in the past decade starting from the end of the 1990s when shows like Friends grabbed the attention, moving from the mid of 2007 when Gossip Girl compelled the audience to be glued to the screens, and finally coming to 2010 onwards when show like The Vampire Diaries have given a completely new genre to viewers to get addicted to. Therefore, a comparative study would be conducted to know the influence of the shows from the 1990s to 2020. This study is carried out to know the influence and effect of these shows on the social behavior, cultural preferences, language, and dress of university students of Lahore.

Statement of Problem

The most threatening problem a nation has to deal with is the threat to its culture. This study is conducted to evaluate the influence of foreign content, in particular the American content that is consumed widely by the youth of this country. This study aims to explore the influence of American television shows like Friends, Gossip Girl, and the Vampire Diaries on the social behavior, cultural preferences, language, and address of university students of Lahore.

Rationale

The rationale of this study is to know the effect of American TV serials on the social behavior, language, norms, habits, and approaches of the university students of Lahore. These university students are young adults and they are the ones who will lead the society and country in the future. And if these youngsters get affected by foreign content and this affects changes their language, behavior, culture, and norms, then this could be a threat to the culture and traditions of our society.

Objectives

1. To determine the influence of Friends, Gossip Girl, and the Vampire Diaries on the social behavior of students.
2. To evaluate the effect of Friends, Gossip Girl, and the Vampire Diaries on the cultural preferences of students.
3. To find out the impact of Friends, Gossip Girl, and the Vampire Diaries on the language and dressing of students.

Research Questions

The research questions for this research are as follows:

R1: Is there any influence of American TV shows Friends, Gossip Girl, and the Vampire Diaries on the social behavior of university students in Lahore?

R2: Is there any effect of Friends, Gossip Girl, and the Vampire Diaries on the cultural preferences and norms of university students in Lahore?

R3: Is there any impact of Friends, Gossip Girl, and the Vampire Diaries on the language and dressing of university students of Lahore?

Literature Review

The success of transnational brands and corporations is evidence that Marshall McLuhan's prediction of the Global Village is coming true. The transnational mass media is frequently blamed in the lead for the globalization of culture. Modern media innovations like satellite channels and the Internet have produced a strong link between audiences across the globe. It is obvious that the youths in various parts of the world are familiar with and are adopting the Western lifestyle of rock music, beverages, dressing, etc. with help of global media. This explains to some extent, the mass media's allegedly enormous impact on the cultural globalization process (Kraidy, 2002).

Pennycook (2013) examined the idea which is communicated in all living expressions as the tendency to rule and consolidate the world into a single framework. Globalization implies applying a worldwide character to things and particularly to make the extent of the use of things worldwide. Globalization thus can infiltrate and deliver enormous consequences for the minds of individuals.

Research by Riaz and Arif (2017) found that there is a strong connection between the disclosures of a foreign television program and its influence on the cultural attitudes of youth. It is clear from the research that youth take a deep influence on lifestyle, fashion, and language from foreign entertainment

channels, especially western media. The proficiency to speak the Urdu language youth has also been affected greatly by foreign media and English culture.

Acculturation is where one's qualities, practices, and mentalities change because of presentation to intercultural contact. According to the study by Morgan & Shanahan (2010), media assumes a key function in cultivating acculturation, particularly as well-known entertainment programs. The impact of TV has been analyzed from different viewpoints, for example, a comparison between degrees of TV utilization, the preferred technique for getting to TV content, and the connection between mass communications cycles and TV exposure.

Qureshi, Baber & Abbas (2021) conducted a cross-sectional survey of university students and the outcome shows that Western culture seems to have a great influence on the social attitudes of university students. Every aspect of university life has been strongly influenced by Western culture, from peer acceptance to local cultures. The research revealed that Western culture has had an impact on even the minutest aspects of daily campus life, leading to generally adverse lifestyle patterns for young students.

A study based on Davison's (1983) third-person effect hypothesis, collected data from almost 2000 Asian and European students. The results demonstrate that whereas the majority of European respondents opine that exposure to American media content hurts their cultural values, the majority of Asian participants think that exposure to this media has a good impact. Overall, all individuals claimed that the effects of mediated violence in American media were detrimental to both themselves and other nations (Willnat et al., 2002).

Data collected from 225 senior students of the Philippine's three high schools revealed that the contrasting cultural picture portrayed by the content of US television shows, being broadcast in the Philippines society, causes students of high school to focus more on non-traditional values (Tan, Tan & Tan, 1987).

In his study on the impact of international media on Pakistani culture, Juni (2014) found that young people frequently watch international media to keep them occupied and for recreation. Through television programs, young people not only learn about new cultural trends but also adapt to those trends. The youth embrace western clothing for all kinds of occasions. They enjoy consuming fast food and conversing in other dialects like Hindi or English. Foreign TV networks frequently promote western values that are in contrast to regional cultural and religious norms.

Morozova (2010) evaluated that cultural imperialism isn't restricted to the dress, way of life, standards, and values of a nation yet now the language has likewise been added to the list. The languages were authentic before globalization occurred. Presently after this

Languages have been attacked. It's observed that presently regardless of what language one is talking in, he/she will utilize English words in it.

Researchers studied the impact of global media on youth and discovered that those who are subjected are heavily influenced. They studied Bangladeshi youth culture which is blending with western culture. The younger generation prefers fast food, modern clothing, a western-style family and marriage institute, as well as western movies, songs, and festivities. They now have a distinctive culture that includes their cuisine, clothing, and entertainment preferences. A specific young culture has been produced by global media with by promotion of foreign culture (Hossin & Mohiuddin, 2015).

Herman & Chomsky (2002) stated that TV "produces consent" and consent allows the organ processor the power of all - the ability to characterize reality. Television has been utilized as a propaganda tool throughout history as is today. There is no uncertainty that TV is the most powerful medium thus it is the most persuasive one too.

In a study of gender stereotypes by Browne (1998), analysis was used to investigate gender stereotypes and violence in children's television advertising and programming in the United States and Australia. Research shows that in all country girls are generally portrayed as passive, respectful, shy, and intelligent.

In contrast, men are generally portrayed as constructive, determined, strong, independent, and successful under this rubric. Subtle elements of self-presentation, including posture, body language, and facial expressions, have been found to suggest gender stereotypes.

Theoretical Framework

Cultivation Theory

Cultivation theory was presented by Gerbner and Gross (1976) and this theory mainly talks about the long-term effects of television content on viewers. The idea was introduced by George Gerbner in his publication "Towards 'Cultural Indicators': The Analysis of Mass Mediated Public Message Systems" where he argues that "changes in the mass production and rapid distribution of messages across previous barriers of time, space, and social grouping bring about systematic variations in public message content whose full significance rests in the cultivation of collective consciousness about elements of existence" (Gerbner, 1969, p. 138). This theory states that what people see on their screens, they perceive as reality and start believing it, accepting it, and following it with time. It also advocates the fact that television content greatly influences the habits and attitudes of youth.

This theory explores the content shown by the western media and the impact on the audience over time. If viewers are exposed to a certain culture or a habit or message over and over, eventually it will change their perception of reality. Heavy viewing of television results in cultivating attitudes and norms and it can deeply penetrate our culture. This theory affirms that television content directly influences the thinking abilities of viewers that in turn leads to a change in cultural attributes. Therefore, this theory very strongly supports the aim of this study that heavy exposure to American television shows influences the social behavior, cultural preferences, and language and dressing of youth.

Cultural Imperialism Theory

Schiller (1973) conferred the theory of cultural imperialism according to which viewers around the world are strongly affected by the media content shown to them, specifically manufactured from the western side of the globe. The cultural imperialism theory owns that most of the media content shown in different states of the world is bought from western media as they have advanced technology and are economically more stable and can create more content due to plenty of resources. Different countries choose to pay the western media to get the content instead of producing their own as they lack the expertise and it is cheaper to buy content from the western media. "Media imperialism theory reflects an over-concentration of mass media from larger nations as a significant variable in negatively affecting smaller nations, in which the national identity of smaller nations is lessened or lost due to media homogeneity inherent in mass media from the larger countries" (Boyd-Barrett, 1977).

Pakistani industry is slowly letting go of its cultural norms and traditions for which it was famous earlier. They are doing so by imitating the western media, broadcasting foreign content on Pakistani channels, and arranging shows and gatherings similar to them, the imitation of foreign fashion trends, dresses, lifestyles, and language is an evident example of the increasing influence of foreign content on our industry that in turn will influence our society and culture.

This proves that the influence of this western content on the language or lifestyle of youth is invading the social and cultural system of Pakistan. Studies show that continuous exposure to television programs of different languages and cultures directly influence the lifestyle, fashion sense, dressing preferences, and language of the viewers.

Methodology

This research article uses both quantitative and qualitative methods. In the quantitative method,

questionnaire-based survey analysis is used as the research methodology, and for this purpose questionnaire is designed that has mostly closed-ended questions. All the students currently enrolled in the public and private universities of Lahore are the universe of the study, the population is the students of four different universities that are Lahore University of Management Sciences (LUMS), Kinnaird College for Women (KC), Punjab University (PU) and university of Central Punjab (UCP). The researcher used simple random sampling for collecting a sample size of 300 students between the ages of 17 to 25 years. The data is then analyzed using SPSS software, the percentage is calculated and the results are depicted by pie-charts to make it look more presentable and easier to understand.

For the qualitative method, in-depth interviews are conducted to collect data for the study. By using the purposive sampling technique, a sample size of 15 students, who are heavy viewers of the shows, is collected from the above-mentioned four universities of Lahore. The collected data was decoded and analyzed to get the hidden meanings and actual themes of it. Different indicators, their influence, and the degree of influence it was measured and results were derived.

Findings & Discussion

The media now is globalized, making people aware of different cultures and traditions around the globe. However, at times, this awareness is so much that a certain culture becomes a part of other's life. Different studies show that media globalization has done a lot of damage to the cultures of different nations by making access to foreign content easy which in turn it threatens the culture and traditions of the receiver nations (Waisbord & Morris, 2001). The decreased cultural limitations are due to the easy availability of media content to people, causing people to accept what the media owners want them to adopt. This is a very prominent way of cultural imperialism.

Television is a very strong tool that has been used for promoting propaganda for a very long time, regardless of the heterogeneous audience (Chadwick 2017; Webster and Ksiazek 2012). The powerful countries, which are economically strong, use television for their benefit and promote their agendas in other countries that are not strong enough to counter this propaganda. In today's world, the strongest countries are the western countries specifically America and that is why they are ruling the media industry. Every country is watching its content that portrays American culture and values very beautifully to the world. This portrayal is invading the cultures of other nations very subtly and people watching this content are readily accepting everything that is shown to them including their culture, social behaviors, dress, and even language. The biggest example of it is that the "Jeans culture" is so common globally that it is considered a universal dress. Similarly, English is considered the universal language spoken in every country of the world, and more than 90% of content online is in English.

The major finding about the objective *"To determine the influence of American TV serials Friends, Gossip Girl, and the Vampire Diaries on the social behavior of university students in Lahore"* is that the respondents of the research believe that the youth is now following the western behaviors and even are proud of them. The dating system, nuclear family systems, moving out at turning a legal age, marrying and divorcing at their convenience, and smoking and drinking openly are all behaviors that are common in the west. Through American shows, these things penetrated our society and today, youngsters are freely practicing these things. The majority of the interviewees claimed that these shows had been one of the reasons for changing traditional concepts of society.

Following are the most important questions and the responses to them that show the change in the social behavior of the university students of Lahore is due to the influence of American television shows.

Table 1: Influence on social behavior

Questions	Very much	Not at all	To some extent
In all three shows, marriages and divorces were taken very casually. Do you think this has affected the sanctity of marriage for the youth?	38.9%	18.6%	42.5%
Do you think that the intimate scenes in these shows can make our youth follow suit?	44.4%	16.7%	38.9%
Do you think the use of alcohol and drugs in American shows has increased over the past 3 decades?	55.9%	13.4%	30.7%
Do you think that American shows have made university students more blunt, disrespectful, and unethical?	30.1%	20.9%	49%
Do you believe these shows can improve the personality traits of the viewers as they had messages about friendship, honesty, and trust in them?	42.2%	20.6%	57.5%
Do you think these shows, by showing messages of Integrity, friendship, care and love promoting these qualities in viewers?	31.4%	10.5%	58.2%

Another major finding of the research on the question is about the cultural preferences of university students. The objective *“To evaluate the effect of Friends, Gossip Girl, and the Vampire Diaries on the culture and norms of university students in Lahore”* has been proven clearly through the result of the survey. About **85% of respondents** agreed that youth get inspired by foreign celebrities’ appearances and styles which help to adopt foreign culture primarily western culture. The Pakistani youth is taking inspiration from these shows in changing their lifestyle, fashion behavior, and cultural norms. These shows create an environment to indulge western culture that's the major reason for cultural transformation. The availability and easy access to American shows through television and the internet have made a traditional shift.

TABLE 2: Influence on cultural preferences

Questions	Very much	Not at all	To some extent
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Nowadays, a lot of youngsters get excited about Christmas, Black Friday, Easter, etc as they saw these festivals in American shows. Do you think these shows have promoted American culture and values in our society?	52.6%	12.4%	35%
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Through American shows, the festivals and traditions of the west are very well known by people all over the world where American content is consumed. The same is the case with Pakistani youth, but one thing that is very prominent in Pakistan is that the students in different universities are keen to celebrate western festivals and carnivals than their occasions. Festivals like Easter, Thanks Giving, Christmas, Black Friday, Halloween, etc. are celebrated in different universities every year along with fashion carnivals, prom nights, and theme weeks but the same people are not excited to celebrate national and traditional occasions like Eid festivals or other special occasions.

In this study, the objective *“To find out the impact of Friends, Gossip Girl, and the Vampire Diaries on the language and dressing of university students of Lahore”* had been explained very well. To the literature review, of the research by Riaz and Arif (2017), the relationship between American TV shows and the dressing of our youth is very clearly visible. **86.3% of the survey respondents** believe that people do get inspired by the characters they see on screen, and this is very common now if we see the western dresses, the jeans, and the tops used by students in universities. They even buy those clothes from brands that are more prominent in the west. **12 out of 15 interviewees** claimed that their fashion behavior has been strongly influenced by American shows. It mainly depends upon how heavy a viewer a person is and how they take their own national and regional dressing. Dressing preferences among youth are changing and it has penetrated deep into the culture. Hence it is proved that exposure to shows especially foreign entertainment had influenced the fashion behavior of Pakistani youth. The inclination of youth towards western dressing is observed from the responses of interviewees.

Table 3: Influence on dressing

Questions	Very much	Not at all	To some extent
The dress shown in these shows is contradictory to Pakistani culture and traditions. Do you think these shows have changed the dressing sense of university students?	39.2%	13.7%	47.1%

Regarding the influence on language, the research shows that **89.5% of the survey respondents** believed that American shows greatly influence the language of university students and more than good; it is in a bad way. About **13 out of 15 interviewees** accepted that even their language has been greatly affected by the binge-watching of American shows.

Table 4: Influence on language

Questions	Very much	Not at all	To some extent
In all three shows, there was excessive usage of abuse, slang, and curse words. Do you feel that university students started using such language in daily life?	41.8%	10.5%	47.7%

The potentially offensive and profane language and gestures are linked with sexual references, body parts, and specifically discriminatory language. The general swear words that aren't acceptable in Pakistani society have been normalized now. Many of the words that are discriminatory on religious bases are common among youngsters. People are using slang and abuse very frequently and in open settings not realizing how disrespectful it is to others. The influence is somewhat positive that people learned the English language and now can speak it more fluently but this led to another setback because in trying to learn and speak English, the student left Urdu and now, some people can't read or write proper Urdu language. Following the literature review, Morozova (2010) clearly describes that the audience uses English words in their respective talk. Regardless of whether they know the English language or not. Even while speaking, the students can't form a few sentences in pure Urdu without including English words in it.

Another important point to be highlighted is the comparison of 3 decades. The respondents believed that the content of American TV shows has seen a huge shift in the past 3 decades. Initially, in the 1990s, the content was less violent, it had more messages in it and was enjoyable and in the 2000s it changed to be more violent, blunt, and absurd. But in the last decade of 2010-2020, the content has been extremely violent, with excessive usage of drugs, alcohol, and nudity in it. About 87.5% of survey respondents believe that obscene content has increased among Americans shown in the last 3 decades.

Table 5: increase in obscene content

Questions	Very much	Not at all	To some extent
Do you believe that over these 3 decades, the vulgarity/obscenity quotient has increased in American shows?	57.8%	11.4%	30.7%

82.7% of respondents believe that the proportion of violence has also increased in the last few decades. 75% of interviewees agree with the statement that over time violence has been normalized by the shows. The continuous depiction of violence has made youth intolerant and results in the development of other negative characteristics. The other 25% of interviewees stated that normalization of violence is not only because of shows but depends on the ones surrounding in which he/she is brought up.

Table 6: increase in violent content

Questions	Very much	Not at all	To some extent
Do you feel that from FRIENDS to GossipGirl to Vampire Diaries, the proportion of violent content has increased in American shows over the decades?	45.4%	17.3%	37.3%

All this discussion simply leads to the conclusion that American content is influencing the university students of Lahore to a great extent. This influence is not healthy for the identity of the people of Pakistan as they will lose their traditions, values, and culture. This means that American content has evolved in the last 3 decades and has become more dangerous and a threat to Pakistani culture and society. About 77.8% of survey respondents also believe that the increasing influence of American TV shows is a threat to Pakistani traditions and norms, to a great extent if not completely.

Table 7: Threat to Pakistani traditions

Questions	Very much	Not at all	To some extent
In light of the above-mentioned question, do you believe that these shows are a threat to Pakistani traditions and norms??	32.7%	22.2%	45.1%

Conclusion

This research was conducted to know the influence of American TV shows on the cultural preferences, social behaviors, language, and dress of the university students of Lahore. By seeing the results of this research, it is very clear that the overall influence of these shows has majorly been negative in our society. These shows have made our youngsters more prone to American culture and values. Their dress and language have been affected so much that they wear western clothes as it's their traditional dress and they prefer to converse in their language and also try to adopt their accent because they think it would look cool and is appreciated by their peers.

The youth have tilted towards American traditions, their events and festivals are celebrated as our own nowadays, and last but not the least, the normal, day-to-day social behavior of our youth has become what American shows portrayed. The acceptance of certain things, like drinking, smoking, and short-term relationships, which are contrary to our cultural and religious values, are becoming normal and acceptable. As Qamar et al. (2012) conclude in their study Cable Television is bolstering cultural diffusion in the country and these television channels and shows are impacting youth's attire, language, family life, and lifestyle choices in addition to their mental and social growth.

Another important point is the shift in content in the past decades. It has been observed that American shows have become more violent, aggressive, and extreme in the last 3 decades. This has induced a greater level of threat to Pakistani culture, as the youth watches these shows and they are getting highly influenced by the violent depiction in these shows. As Shafayat (2019) reinforced that media takes a very significant part in the creation and preservation of social and cultural norms in our society. A substantial part of cultural transmission involves television because it is a promising medium for the dissemination of cultural values.

Nevertheless, the influence has been good at some point as it taught traits like truthfulness, honesty, and the value of friendship, family, and relationships to its viewers. Moreover, by seeing the foreign content, the English-speaking skills and vocabulary of our people also enhanced, but no matter how positive the influence of American shows is, every nation should stick to its own culture, traditions, and language if they want to make their place in the world otherwise, soon, they would forget their own identity making their existence extinct.

Limitations

- The lockdown, and closure of universities didn't allow getting a bigger sample for surveys and interviews.
- The limited sample of students didn't allow the researchers to conduct the study on a bigger level.
- The interviews were also not conducted in person but on zoom meetings, due to which a lot of interviews were short and to the point rather than in-depth.

Recommendations

- Researchers in the future should highlight this topic with more specific examples and they should also highlight the destruction of Pakistani culture and traditions due to American influence.
- Further researchers use a larger sample size and they should also choose another method of data collection, such as focus group discussions to know the viewpoint of people who are specialized in their fields and to have a wholesome discussion to know the results in depth.
- The upcoming studies should have to be on shows of the same genre.

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